

PRODIGEES

*Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe
Towards Sustainable Development*

D3.1 R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment

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R&I Publications on Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment

Researchers prepare at least one R&I publication per secondment on the approved research topic. Publications can be working papers, journal articles, book chapters, policy briefs, concept papers, or similar publication.

Secondments and their accompanying deliverables take place within Work Package 2: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Governance and Society or Work Package 3: Digitalisation for Sustainability in Economy and Environment. At the onset of the secondment, in the Researcher Declaration Form, researchers indicate whether their research topic falls within WP2 or WP3. The following list of academic citations are the list of publications that PRODIGEES researchers produced within the theme of WP3. As further publications are forthcoming, including an edited volume as a main project research result, the list is not yet exhaustive. All published work from PRODIGEES is available in the project's online repository, "PRODIGEES Research Community", on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/prodigees/records>

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